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O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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TECHNOLOGIES FOR FORMING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE BASED ON INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION

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Abstract: This article provides a general overview of technologies for developing students' communicative competence based on interdisciplinary integration. It examines effective pedagogical technologies aimed at improving communicative competence in the educational process through interdisciplinary approaches. The successful development of future teachers' communicative competence is considered a key factor in elevating the teaching profession to the level of art, as it enables educators to effectively teach and guide dozens or hundreds of learners. One of the most important and responsible tasks facing teachers in our republic is the preparation of specialists who view the world with a new perspective, demonstrate initiative and resourcefulness, possess entrepreneurial skills, and contribute to building and strengthening the foundations of a prosperous future. The conclusions presented in the article can be effectively applied in pedagogical practice.

Key words: interdisciplinary integration, electronic educational resources, integration, communicative competence, technology, science, teacher, pedagogy.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada fanlararo integratsiyaga asoslangan holda talabalarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish texnologiyalari haqida umumiy ma'lumot berilgan. Tadqiqotda ta'lim jarayonida fanlararo integratsiya asosida kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishga xizmat qiluvchi samarali pedagogik texnologiyalar yoritilgan. Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini muvaffaqiyatli rivojlantirish ularning kasbiy faoliyatini san'at darajasiga ko'tarish, o'nlab va yuzlab ta'lim oluvchilarga samarali ta'lim berish imkonini yaratadi. Shuningdek, respublikamiz o'qituvchilari oldida turgan eng muhim va mas'uliyatli vazifalardan biri – dunyoga yangicha nigoh bilan qaraydigan, tashabbuskor, tadbirkorlik ko'nikmalariga ega hamda buyuk kelajagimiz poydevorini barpo etuvchi mutaxassislarni tayyorlashdan iborat. Maqolada keltirilgan xulosalardan pedagogik jarayonlarda samarali foydalanish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: fanlararo integratsiya, elektron ta'lim resurslari, integratsiya, kommunikativ kompetensiya, texnologiya, fan, o'qituvchi, pedagogika.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены общие сведения о технологиях формирования и развития коммуникативной компетентности студентов на основе межпредметной интеграции. Рассматриваются современные педагогические технологии, обеспечивающие повышение уровня коммуникативной компетентности студентов в образовательном процессе на междисциплинарной основе. Успешное развитие коммуникативной компетентности будущих учителей рассматривается как важнейшее условие возведения педагогической профессии на уровень искусства, позволяющего эффективно обучать и воспитывать десятки и сотни обучающихся. Одной из наиболее значимых и ответственных задач, стоящих перед учителями нашей республики, является подготовка специалистов, способных по-новому воспринимать окружающий мир, проявлять инициативность, заниматься предпринимательской деятельностью и создавать основу для устойчивого развития будущего. Выводы, представленные в статье, могут быть использованы в педагогическом процессе.

Ключевые слова: межпредметная интеграция, электронные образовательные ресурсы, интеграция, коммуникативная компетентность, технологии, наука, учитель, педагогика.

INTRODUCTION

The implementation of interdisciplinary integration in the education system is one of the most relevant contemporary issues. The introduction of integration into education plays a special role in increasing students' interest in science. Before discussing interdisciplinary integration, it is necessary to address fundamental questions such as what integration is and how it can or cannot be effectively applied in the educational process.

Today, the main task of professors and teachers working in higher education institutions is to develop scientific research, provide high-quality education to students in accordance with the requirements of educa-

tional standards through the effective use of modern information technologies, and continuously monitor their academic activities. They are also responsible for providing scientific and methodological assistance, teaching students how to effectively use information flows, and developing their ability to work independently. The introduction of advanced interactive educational technologies based on the effective use of modern information and communication technologies and tools, together with the continuous improvement of the scientific and pedagogical potential and professional skills of professors and teachers, can guarantee the preparation of globally minded and highly qualified personnel for a steadily developing economy.

A number of reforms are being implemented to develop the higher education system. In this regard, the Decree "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", adopted on 2019-10-08^[1], serves as the legal basis for these reforms. Furthermore, on 2020-10-06, Resolution PQ-4851 titled "On Measures to Further Improve the Education System in the Field of Information Technology, Develop Scientific Research, and Integrate It with the IT Industry" was adopted^[2]. The resolution states that improving the personnel training system in the field of information technologies is one of the key conditions for the successful implementation of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, the development of digital technologies, and their wide application in the daily life of the population. In addition, it emphasizes that the measures taken to increase the efficiency of professional training and retraining systems in the field of information technologies create a solid foundation for providing state bodies and sectoral organizations with qualified IT specialists.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Interdisciplinary integration has been widely discussed in pedagogical research as an effective approach to improving the quality of education and developing key competencies in learners. In the context of higher education reforms in Uzbekistan, state норматив-huquqiy hujjatlar such as the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 2019-10-08 emphasize the modernization of education through integration, digitalization, and competence-based approaches. These policy documents highlight interdisciplinary integration as a strategic tool for linking theory with practice and ensuring holistic professional training.

The theoretical foundations of interdisciplinary integration are closely related to the competence-based approach to education. Bermus and Lebedev explain that competence-based education shifts the focus from simple knowledge transfer to the formation of practical skills and professional readiness. Zimnyaya and Klyuchevnykh note that competencies represent a new paradigm of educational outcomes, where communicative competence plays a central role in a student's social and professional development. These theoretical views provide a basis for understanding how interdisciplinary integration contributes to the formation of communicative competence.

Researchers in Uzbekistan have paid particular attention to the relationship between digital technologies and interdisciplinary integration. Abdurazzokova and Kuchkarova argue that digitalization significantly enhances the effectiveness of integration by enabling interactive learning environments and interdisciplinary collaboration. Sharipova highlights that communicative competence is formed not only through subject knowledge but also through psychological and pedagogical conditions created by integrated and technology-supported instruction. These studies demonstrate that interdisciplinary integration strengthens communication skills when combined with modern educational technologies.

International research also confirms the importance of interdisciplinary and digital approaches in developing learners' communicative competence. Robinson and Galloway emphasize that digital education supports interdisciplinary interaction and collaborative learning, which are essential for communication development. Smith and Brown point out that interactive technologies encourage active participation, dialogue, and critical thinking, thereby improving communicative competence in digital learning environments. These findings align with the idea that integration and technology together enhance educational outcomes.

Empirical studies by Mamatkulova and Tangirov further support the effectiveness of interdisciplinary and digital approaches in education. Their research shows that electronic educational resources and individualized learning technologies promote students' active involvement and communication skills. Studies published in national and international journals demonstrate that interdisciplinary integration, combined with digital tools, creates favorable conditions for developing communicative competence and preparing students for professional activities in a rapidly changing educational environment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Integration (from the Latin *integratio* – restoration, completion, wholeness) is understood as the convergence and interconnection of academic disciplines in the course of a differential process. The integration process represents a stage of establishing relationships among disciplines at a new and higher qualitative level, which

requires the ability to demonstrate knowledge in a comprehensive and systematic manner. It should be noted that the roots of the integration process can be traced back to folk and scientific pedagogy of the distant past. K. D. Ushinsky emphasized the spiritual and pedagogical nature of didactic influence and the psychological-pedagogical interconnection within folk pedagogy, stating that the knowledge and ideas imparted by any science represent a broad and enlightening view of the world and life. Even at that time, scholars emphasized that the use of connections between sciences, that is, the integration of knowledge, makes it possible to perceive life in a holistic and comprehensive way. Interdisciplinary integration remains a necessary condition for modern education today.

Excessive categorization of textbooks often suppresses students' interest in learning and creates the impression that further discovery is impossible. The rapid development of teaching principles and methods, constant updates of curricula and textbooks, and the emergence of new educational institutions have not eliminated the predominance of informational overload over personal development in modern schooling. For this reason, interdisciplinary integration is becoming one of the most important factors in contemporary educational development. The psychological and philosophical foundations of interdisciplinary integration can be found in the works of I. P. Pavlov and I. M. Sechenov. A learner may not always effectively retain existing or new information within a single subject; however, when topics are enriched with content from other disciplines and presented in an interconnected manner, learning becomes more engaging and easier to remember. Nature itself also demonstrates interconnected events and phenomena.

The objective basis for combining scientific knowledge lies in the holistic picture of the world, as well as in the commonality of research methods used in the process of cognition. The principle of systematicity serves as the philosophical foundation of interdisciplinary integration. Integration helps eliminate fragmentation and mosaic thinking in students' knowledge, promotes comprehensive learning, and contributes to the formation of universal human values. Both domestic and foreign pedagogy have accumulated substantial experience in addressing integration issues. At different historical periods, scholars such as J. A. Comenius, I. G. Pestalozzi, J. J. Rousseau, L. N. Tolstoy, and K. D. Ushinsky actively applied interdisciplinary integration within the educational process. As the 21st century is an era of technology, the rapid growth of information volume has become a natural phenomenon, while the ability to perceive and comprehend this information has significantly decreased. A viable solution lies in the synthesis of various disciplines, the development of integrated courses, and the establishment of interrelations among all academic subjects.

Today, the main ideas of integrative education include the following:

1. A learner-centered focus of education as a human-value-oriented process;
2. Formation of generalized subject structures and methods of activity, ensuring mastery of knowledge based on understanding underlying principles;
3. Priority of meaning-forming motives in education, including internal, external, motivational, and organizational factors;
4. Consistency in learning through understanding internal connections within scientific theories;
5. Problem-based learning;
6. Reflection on learning activities;
7. Dialogism, based on the principle that truth emerges through dialogical communication. The primary goal of integrative education is the formation of a holistic worldview.

Within the framework of integrated learning, several key technologies can be distinguished:

1. Integrative technologies;
2. Project-based technologies;
3. Educational technologies within the global information society;
4. Teaching large-scale systematic educational courses using Internet-based platforms.

When planning integrated lessons, the following aspects should be considered:

1. Knowledge blocks are combined, so it is essential to clearly define the main objective of the lesson;
2. Information required to achieve the objective is derived from the content of academic subjects;
3. Multiple connections are established within the educational material;

4. Components of integrated content represent an essential element of the lesson and are planned for a concluding synthesis;
5. Teaching methods and instructional tools must be carefully selected, and students' cognitive workload during the lesson should be appropriately determined.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The process of integration requires certain conditions to be met. The objects of study must be identical or sufficiently close in content; the integrated subjects should apply the same or similar research methods; and they must be organized on the basis of common regularities and theoretical concepts.

Let us now consider the advantages and disadvantages of integration. First, integration enables the implementation of one of the most important principles of didactics – the principle of systematic learning. Second, it creates optimal conditions for the development of thinking, logic, adaptability, and critical reasoning. Third, it promotes the formation of a systemic worldview and contributes to the harmonization of students' personalities. As a result, subject fragmentation is reduced, interdisciplinary links expand and deepen, and students gain access to a broader and more integrated body of knowledge. Fourth, integration acts as an effective motivational tool, supports students' active engagement, and stimulates cognitive and creative activity. At the same time, the negative aspects of integration include increased lesson intensity, possible incompleteness of detailed content, the emergence of isolated cases, and the fact that lesson preparation requires a considerable amount of time.

Success in developing the communicative competence of future teachers is regarded as elevating the teaching profession to the level of art and enabling educators to effectively instruct dozens or even hundreds of learners. At the same time, the most important and responsible task facing teachers in our republic is the training of specialists who view the world from a new perspective, demonstrate initiative and resourcefulness, possess entrepreneurial skills, and contribute to building and strengthening the foundation of a prosperous future. A teacher bears social responsibility for education and upbringing within their professional field. Along with continuous improvement of professional qualifications, a teacher must be capable of fulfilling the roles of educator, mentor, and facilitator, which, more broadly, requires well-developed communicative competence. In modern conditions, a teacher must not only acquire theoretical and practical knowledge in their chosen profession but also be able to apply innovative teaching methods and technologies in various educational situations. In other words, a teacher should possess professional competence.

The concept of “competence” and the competence-based approach, which emphasizes the individual as the bearer of competence, have been formed over centuries within the context of national traditions and values. Communicative competence requires a teacher to engage effectively in communication and maintain positive relationships with students and colleagues in diverse situations. Regardless of teaching content, context, or specific objectives, the primary goal of a teacher is to create a “developing environment” in the classroom. This includes motivating students to learn; encouraging them to act independently and actively participate in educational activities; fostering imagination and skill development; searching for necessary information; organizing independent activity through projects and their implementation; understanding work objectives and outcomes and approaching tasks responsibly; determining appropriate levels of complexity for subject content, goals, and tasks; enabling independent selection of forms and methods; teaching students to work collaboratively in project-based activities; identifying problems, distributing tasks, planning, conducting discussions and debates, and evaluating results; facilitating student participation in various discussion formats; developing students' self-regulation skills; and improving learning outcomes through assessment systems that support self-evaluation, achievement analysis, and further development.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Thus, the formation of communicative competence based on interdisciplinary integration not only contributes to students' personal and social development but also prepares them for future professional activities. In this process, the effective use of digital technologies and modern pedagogical approaches plays a crucial role.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that integration in education is not a temporary trend but a fundamental necessity for preparing highly qualified specialists in all spheres of human activity. Integration technologies in modern education ensure the unification of individual scientific domains into a coherent and integrated system. Moreover, this process involves not merely the mechanical combination of different bodies of knowledge but their application through an interdependent and systematic approach, which enables learners to act holistically and consistently when addressing complex problems.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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